
OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories

1.1 Introduction

1.1.1 Aim

The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers 3.0 provide orientation for repository managers to define and implement their local data management policies according to the requirements of the OpenAIRE - Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe.

Initially, the requirements of the OpenAIRE infrastructure, and the previous versions of the OpenAIRE Guidelines, were established to support and monitor the implementation of the [FP7 OA pilot](#). However, this version of the Guidelines, according to the expansion of the aims of the OpenAIRE project and infrastructure, has a broader scope. In fact, these guidelines are intended to guide repository manager to expose to the OpenAIRE infrastructure not only EC funded publications, but also other Open Access publications, regardless of their funding.

So, by implementing these Guidelines, repository managers will not only be enabling authors who deposit publications in their repository to fulfill the EC Open Access requirements, and eventually also the requirements of other (national or international) funders with whom OpenAIRE cooperates, but also incorporating their publications into the OpenAIRE infrastructure for discoverability and utilizing value-added services provided by the OpenAIRE portal.

According to the ongoing expansion and anticipating the merger of the DRIVER Guidelines into the context of OpenAIRE Guidelines, detailed content from the DRIVER Guidelines 2.0 was adapted and added into this version of the Guidelines. The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers 3.0 are now only a part of a set of OpenAIRE Guidelines that also includes the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archive Managers and the OpenAIRE CERIF-XML profile.

1.1.2 What's new

In comparison with previous versions of the Guidelines, this 3.0 version introduces three main changes:

- The OpenAIRE OAI set has been renamed from `ec_fundedresources` to `openaire`.
- New elements for indicating alternative identifiers, relations to other publications (references), and relations to research datasets have been defined.
- The recommendations on how to use the Dublin Core elements have been inherited from the DRIVER Guidelines.

1.1.3 Acknowledgements & Contributors

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1.1.4 Versions

- 3.0, April 2013
- 3.0, beta December 2012
 - The OpenAIRE OAI set has been renamed from `ec_fundedresources` to `openaire`.
 - New relation elements for indicating external identifiers, references and connections to datasets.
- 2.0, October 2012 doi:10.5281/zenodo.59208
 - Compatibility for aggregators; extended Namespace for Project Identification
- 1.1, November 2010 doi:10.5281/zenodo.59206
 - Correction of names and references; addition of license and version statement
- 1.0, July 2010 doi:10.5281/zenodo.59204
 - Initial document

1.2 Use of OAI-PMH

OpenAIRE uses the [OAI-PMH v2.0](#) protocol for harvesting publication metadata.

1.2.1 Metadata Format

OpenAIRE expects metadata to be encoded in the [Dublin Core](#) metadata format (metadataPrefix `oai_dc`). For information on how to use the individual DC fields, please refer to the section “Use of OAI-DC” below.

OpenAIRE OAI Set

For harvesting the records relevant to OpenAIRE, the use of a specific **OAI-Set** at the local repository is *mandatory*. The set must have the following characteristics:

setName	setSpec
OpenAIRE	openaire

Note: A harvester only uses the **setSpec** value to perform selective harvesting. The letters of the setSpec must be in small caps.

Set content

Publications to be inserted in the OpenAIRE set must conform to **at least one** of the following criteria:

- They are available in Open Access (full text with no access restrictions)
- They are the outcome of a funded research project identified by a project identifier (see below) regardless of their access status (see section below on [[Literature Guidelines: Metadata Field Access Level|Application Profile Field Access Level]]).

1.2.2 Compatibility of aggregators

Besides individual repositories and journals, also aggregators (e.g., on the national level) can become OpenAIRE compatible. In this case, additional provenance information on the original content providers harvested by the aggregator has to be encoded for OpenAIRE. In accordance with the [OAI-PMH guidelines](#), the provenance information has to be provided in the `about` element of an OAI record, as displayed in the following example:

```

1 <about>
2   <provenance xmlns="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance"
3     xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
4     xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance
5       http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance.xsd">
6     <originDescription altered="true" harvestDate="2012-09-17T14:58:36Z">
7       <baseURL>http://dspace.library.uu.nl:8080/dspace-oai/request</baseURL>
8       <identifier>oai:dspace.library.uu.nl:1874/218065</identifier>
9       <datestamp>2012-01-19T12:38:56Z</datestamp>
10      <metadataNamespace>
11        http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc/
12      </metadataNamespace>
13    </originDescription>
14  </provenance>
15 </about>

```

1.3 Use of OAI-DC

1.3.1 OpenAIRE-specific Syntax for OAI-DC

OpenAIRE relies on a specific syntax used in the values of standard Dublin Core metadata fields to identify projects, funders, referenced publications, and datasets. This syntax takes the form of URIs and is defined as the `info:eu-repo` namespace.

This section explains which DC fields to use together with this syntax to correctly mark up the information relevant for OpenAIRE.

Within OpenAIRE the use of the fields is either:

Within OpenAIRE the use of fields are either:

- **Mandatory (M)** = the field must always be present in the metadata record. An empty element is not allowed.
- **Mandatory when applicable (MA)** = when the value of the field can be obtained it must be present in the metadata record.
- **Recommended (R)** = the use of the field is recommended.
- **Optional (O)** = the property may be used to provide complementary information about the resource

A complete example record

```
1 <record>
2   <header>
3     <identifier>oai:repository.example.com:2003292</identifier>
4     <datestamp>2012-11-30T13:40:28Z</datestamp>
5     <setSpec>openaire</setSpec>
6   </header>
7   <metadata>
8     <oai_dc:dc
9       xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/"
10      xmlns:oai_dc="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc/"
11      xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
12      xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc/
13        http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc.xsd">
14       <dc:title>Studies of Unicorn Behaviour</dc:title>
15       <dc:identifier>http://repository.example.org/2003292</dc:identifier>
16       <dc:creator>Jane, Doe</dc:creator>
17       <dc:creator>John, Doe</dc:creator>
18       <dc:description>
19         Lorem ipsum dolor...
20       </dc:description>
21       <dc:subject>info:eu-repo/classification/ddc/590</dc:subject>
22       <dc:subject>Unicorns</dc:subject>
23       <dc:relation>info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/EC/FP7/1234556789/EU//UNICORN</dc:relation>
24       <dc:relation>info:eu-repo/semantics/altIdentifier/eissn/1234-5678</dc:relation>
25       <dc:relation>info:eu-repo/semantics/altIdentifier/pmid/123456789</dc:relation>
26       <dc:relation>info:eu-repo/semantics/altIdentifier/doi/10.1000/182</dc:relation>
27       <dc:relation>info:eu-repo/semantics/reference/doi/10.1234/789.1</dc:relation>
28       <dc:relation>info:eu-repo/semantics/dataset/doi/10.1234/789.1</dc:relation>
29       <dc:rights>info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess</dc:rights>
30       <dc:rights>http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/uk/</dc:rights>
31       <dc:source>Journal Of Unicorn Research</dc:source>
32       <dc:publisher>Unicorn Press</dc:publisher>
33       <dc:date>2013</dc:date>
34       <dc:type>info:eu-repo/semantics/article</dc:type>
35     </oai_dc:dc>
36   </metadata>
37 </record>
```

1.4 Application Profile Overview

This documentation uses the following namespace abbreviation:

- dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>

OpenAIRE-Field	OAI-DC Element	Refinement by vocabulary
<i>Title (M)</i>	dc:title	
<i>Creator (M)</i>	dc:creator	
<i>Project Identifier (MA)</i>	dc:relation	info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/
<i>Access Level (M)</i>	dc:rights	info:eu-repo/semantics/
<i>License Condition (R)</i>	dc:rights	
<i>Embargo End Date (MA)</i>	dc:date	info:eu-repo/date/embargoEnd/
<i>Alternative Identifier (R)</i>	dc:relation	info:eu-repo/semantics/altIdentifier/
<i>Publication Reference (R)</i>	dc:relation	info:eu-repo/semantics/reference/
<i>Dataset Reference (R)</i>	dc:relation	info:eu-repo/semantics/dataset/
<i>Subject (MA)</i>	dc:subject	
<i>Description (MA)</i>	dc:description	
<i>Publisher (MA)</i>	dc:publisher	
<i>Contributor (R)</i>	dc:contributor	
<i>Publication Date (M)</i>	dc:date	
<i>Publication Type (M)</i>	dc:type	info:eu-repo/semantics/
<i>Publication Version (R)</i>	dc:type	info:eu-repo/semantics/
<i>Format (R)</i>	dc:format	
<i>Resource Identifier (M)</i>	dc:identifier	
<i>Source (R)</i>	dc:source	
<i>Language (R)</i>	dc:language	
<i>Relation (O)</i>	dc:relation	
<i>Coverage (R)</i>	dc:coverage	
<i>Audience (R)</i>	dc:audience	

Application Profile:

1.5 Title (M)

1.5.1 DC Field

dc:title

1.5.2 Usage

Mandatory (M)

1.5.3 Usage Instruction

Preserve the original wording, order and spelling of the resource title. Only capitalize proper nouns. Punctuation need not reflect the usage of the original. Subtitles should be separated from the title by a colon. This instruction would result in Title:Subtitle (i.e. no space). If necessary, repeat this element for multiple titles.

1.5.4 Example

```
<dc:title>Main title:Subtitle</dc:title>
```

1.6 Creator (M)

1.6.1 DC Field

dc:creator

1.6.2 Usage

Mandatory

1.6.3 Usage Instruction

Examples of a Creator include a person, an organization, or a service. If necessary, repeat this element for multiple authors.

Use inverted name, so the syntax will be the following: “surname”, “initials” (“first name”) “prefix”. For example Jan Hubert de Smit becomes

```
<dc:creator>Smit, J.H. (John) de</dc:creator>
```

Within the scope of unqualified DC it is recommended to use a standardised writing style for names, use the writing style used by the publisher when this is available. When that is not available use the encoding of the APA bibliographic writing style as in a reference list when applicable. (outside the scope of Unqualified DC more precise and granular formatting methods are available.)

When initials and first name are both available use this formatting:

```
<dc:creator>Janssen, J. (John)</dc:creator>
```

Generational suffixes (Jr., Sr., etc.) should follow the surname. When in doubt, give the name as it appears, and do not invert. Omit titles (like “Dr”). For example: “Dr. John H. de Smit Jr.” becomes

```
<dc:creator>Smit Jr., J.H. (John) de</dc:creator>
```

In the case of an organization name which clearly includes an organizational hierarchy, list the parts of the hierarchy from largest to smallest, separated by full stops.

For example:

```
<dc:creator>Utrecht University. Department of Computer Sciences</dc:creator>
```

If it is not clear whether there is a hierarchy present, or unclear which is the larger or smaller portion of the body, give the name as it appears in the resource. Only encode organisations in this element to indicate corporate authorship, not to indicate the affiliation of an individual.

The inclusion of personal and corporate name headings from authority lists constructed according to local or national thesaurus files is optional.

It is recommended to encode thesauri with an URI, for service providers to recognise the thesaurus schema. For example:

```
<dc:creator>urn:NationalOrgThesaurus:nl/234</dc:creator>
```

In cases of lesser responsibility, other than authorship, use dc:contributor. If the nature of the responsibility is ambiguous, recommended best practice is to use dc:publisher for organizations, and dc:creator for individuals.

1.6.4 Do Not Confuse With

- *Contributor (R)*
- *Publisher (MA)*

1.6.5 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.6.6 Example

```

1 <dc:creator>Evans, R.J.</dc:creator>
2 <dc:creator>Walker Jnr., John</dc:creator>
3 <dc:creator>
4   International Human Genome Sequencing Consortium
5 </dc:creator>
6 <dc:creator>
7   Loughborough University. Department of Computer Science
8 </dc:creator>

```

1.7 Project Identifier (MA)

1.7.1 DC Field

dc:relation

1.7.2 Usage

Mandatory when applicable

1.7.3 Usage Instruction

An authoritative list of projects is exposed by OpenAIRE through OAI-PMH, and available for all repository managers. Values include the project name and project ID. The projectID equals the Grant Agreement identifier, and is defined by the `info:eu-repo` namespace term `grantAgreement`.

The syntax is:

```

info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/Funder/FundingProgram/ProjectID/
[Jurisdiction]/[ProjectName]/[ProjectAcronym]

```

where:

- `Funder` refers to the funding organization (e.g., EC for European Commission, WT for Wellcome Trust)
- `FundingProgramme` refers to a specific programme (e.g., FP7 for Framework Programme Seven, H2020 for Horizon 2020)
- `ProjectID` refers to a unique identifier in the scope of the funder (and maybe the programme), e.g. a grant agreement number.

- Jurisdiction refers to the authority granted to a formally constituted legal body (e.g. EU for European Union)
- ProjectName contains the full name of the project
- ProjectAcronym contains the project's acronym.

For OpenAIRE compatibility, the elements in square brackets are optional. The three-part namespace is *mandatory when applicable* (`info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/Funder/FundingProgram/ProjectID`), while the six-parts namespace is *recommended*.

When omitting fields in the extended version, the number of fields must be preserved by using /. A correct example for omitting the the ProjectName field would therefore look like this: `EC/FP7/12345/EU//OpenAIREplus`

If any of the field values contains a forward slash (/), it needs to be escaped using URL encoding (%2F). For instance, `My/Project` would be represented as `My%2FProject`.

1.7.4 Since

OpenAIRE Guidelines v1

1.7.5 Example

An example utilizing all six fields:

```
1 <dc:relation>
2   info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/EC/FP7/244909/EU/Making Capabilities Work/WorkAble
3 </dc:relation>
```

An example for omitting the the ProjectName field (note that the number of slashes is correctly preserved):

```
1 <dc:relation>
2   info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/EC/FP7/283595/EU//OpenAIREplus
3 </dc:relation>
```

A correct example using the old three-part form (discouraged):

```
1 <dc:relation>
2   info:eu-repo/grantAgreement/EC/FP7/244909
3 </dc:relation>
```

1.8 Access Level (M)

1.8.1 DC Field

`dc:rights`

1.8.2 Usage

Mandatory

1.8.3 Usage Instruction

Use terms from the [info:eu-repo-Access-Terms](#) vocabulary . The values are:

- `info:eu-repo/semantics/closedAccess`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/embargoedAccess`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/restrictedAccess`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess`

1.8.4 Example

```
<dc:rights>info:eu-repo/semantics/openAccess</dc:rights>
```

1.9 License Condition (R)

1.9.1 DC Field

`dc:rights`

1.9.2 Usage

Recommended

1.9.3 DCMI Definition

Information about rights held in and over the resource.

1.9.4 Usage Instruction

Typically, a rights element will contain a rights management statement for the access or use of the object, or reference a service providing such information. Rights information often encompasses Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Copyright, and various Property Rights. It is preferred to refer to a rights service where the reuse rights are made clear to the end-user by using a URL. For example the Creative Commons organisation has created URIs for their different licences in the different jurisdictions. This can be applied to create machine readable usage licenses.

1.9.5 Since

OpenAIRE Guidelines v3

1.9.6 Example

Generic usage examples:

```
1 <dc:rights>(c) University of Bath, 2003</dc:rights>
2 <dc:rights>(c) Andrew Smith, 2003</dc:rights>
```

Using Creative Commons right services, makes the usage rights much more clear to the end user. More information see “Use of Intellectual Property Rights”. In this case Andrew Smith referring to <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/uk/>

```
1 <!-- example 1 -->
2 <dc:rights>
3   http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/uk/
4 </dc:rights>
```

The URL provides the location where the license can be read. With creative common licenses the type of license can be recognized in the URL name itself. A pro for having the license point to an URL in this way, is that this is machine readable.

```
1 <!-- example 2 -->
2 <dc:rights>cc-by-sa, Andrew Smith</dc:rights>
```

The string cc-by-sa provides the licence type in a rough sense. The name is the person or party where the rights apply to.

```
1 <!-- example 3 -->
2 <dc:rights>cc-by-sa, info:eu-repo/dai/nl/344568</dc:rights>
```

or:

```
1 <dc:rights>cc-by-nc-sa, urn:isni:234562-2</dc:rights>
```

Also a Digital Author Identifier (DAI) or International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI) can be used to globally uniquely identify persons and organisations and relate these names with the appropriate rights.

1.10 Embargo End Date (MA)

1.10.1 DC Field

dc:date

1.10.2 Usage

Mandatory when applicable

1.10.3 Usage Instruction

When *Access Level (M)* is set to

- info:eu-repo/semantics/embargoedAccess

the end date of the embargo period must be provided. The corresponding term is defined by

- info:eu-repo/date/embargoEnd/<YYYY-MM-DD>

Encoding of this date should be in the form YYYY-MM-DD conforming to ISO 8601.

1.10.4 Since

OpenAIRE Guidelines v1

1.10.5 Example

```
1 <dc:date>info:eu-repo/date/embargoEnd/2015-12-31</dc:date>
```

1.11 Alternative Identifier (R)

1.11.1 DC Field

```
dc:relation
```

1.11.2 Usage

Recommended

1.11.3 Usage Instruction

List alternative identifiers for this publication that are not the primary identifier (repository splash page), e.g., the DOI of publisher's version, the PubMed/arXiv ID. The term is defined by `info:eu-repo/semantics/altIdentifier/<scheme>/<identifier>` where `<scheme>` must be one of the following:

- `ark` – Archival Resource Key
- `arxiv` – arXiv.org identifier
- `doi` – Digital Object Identifier
- `hdl` – Handle
- `isbn` – International Standard Book Number
- `piissn` – International Standard Serial Number (print version)
- `eissn` – International Standard Serial Number (electronic Version)
- `pmid` – PubMed ID
- `purl` – Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
- `urn` – Uniform Resource Name
- `wos` – Web of Science accession number

1.11.4 Since

OpenAIRE Guidelines v3

1.11.5 Example

```
1 <dc:relation>
2   info:eu-repo/semantics/altIdentifier/doi/10.1234/789.1
3 </dc:relation>
```

1.12 Publication Reference (R)

1.12.1 DC Field

dc:relation

1.12.2 Usage

Recommended

1.12.3 Usage Instruction

Encode links to publications referenced by this publication. The syntax is: `info:eu-repo/semantics/reference/<scheme>/<identifier>` where `<scheme>` must be one of the following:

- `ark` – Archival Resource Key
- `arxiv` – arXiv.org identifier
- `doi` – Digital Object Identifier
- `hdl` – Handle
- `isbn` – International Standard Book Number
- `issn` – International Standard Serial Number
- `pmid` – PubMed ID
- `purl` – Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
- `url` – Uniform Resource Locator
- `urn` – Uniform Resource Name
- `wos` – Web of Science accession number

1.12.4 Since

OpenAIRE Guidelines v3

1.12.5 Example

```
1 <dc:relation>
2   info:eu-repo/semantics/reference/doi/10.1234/789.1
3 </dc:relation>
```

1.13 Dataset Reference (R)

1.13.1 DC Field

dc:relation

1.13.2 Usage

Recommended

1.13.3 Usage Instruction

Encodes links to research datasets connected with this publication. The syntax is: `info:eu-repo/semantics/dataset/<scheme>/<identifier>` where `<scheme>` must be one of the following:

- `ark` – Archival Resource Key
- `doi` – Digital Object Identifier
- `hdl` – Handle
- `purl` – Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
- `url` – Uniform Resource Locator
- `urn` – Uniform Resource Name

1.13.4 Since

OpenAIRE Guidelines v3

1.13.5 Example

```
1 <dc:relation>
2   info:eu-repo/semantics/dataset/doi/10.1234/789.1
3 </dc:relation>
```

1.14 Subject (MA)

1.14.1 DC Field

`dc:subject`

1.14.2 Usage

Mandatory when applicable (MA)

1.14.3 Usage Instruction

In the DC subject element two kinds of values are possible: encode either a keyword or a classification. When both are available use separate occurrences of this element.

Use the first occurrence of the DC element `subject` for a human readable keyword.

In general, choose the most significant and unique words for keywords, avoiding those too general to describe a particular resource. If the subject of the resource is a person or an organization, use the same form of the name as you would if the person or organization were an author, but do not repeat the name in the `dc:creator` element.

For keywords/keyphrases that are not controlled by a vocabulary or thesaurus either encode multiple terms with a semi-colon separating each keyword/keyphrase; or repeat the element for each term. There are no requirements regarding the capitalization of keywords though internal (within archive) consistency is recommended.

Where terms are taken from a standard classification schema: encode each term in a separate element. Encode the complete subject descriptor according to the relevant scheme. Use the capitalisation and punctuation used in the original scheme.

It is recommended to use an URI when using classification schemes or controlled vocabularies especially when codified schemes are used DDC or UDC. Service providers can recognise encoding schemas more easily when the schema is “URI-fied” by an authority namespace. When the classification scheme is codified, use a human readable text of the code, preferably in English, directly below the codified element. For example:

```
1 <dc:subject>info:eu-repo/classification/ddc/641</dc:subject>
2 <dc:subject>Anatomy</dc:subject>
```

If no specific classification scheme is used we recommend the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC). The first 1000 terms is called the Dewey Decimal Classification Summary and can be downloaded at <http://www.oclc.org/dewey/resources/summaries/> if one agrees with the following terms and conditions: <http://www.oclc.org/research/researchworks/ddc/terms.htm>

1.14.4 Do Not Confuse With

- *Publication Type (M)*

1.14.5 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.14.6 Example

```
1 <dc:subject>
2   polar oceanography; boundary current; masstransport; water masses;
3   halocline; mesoscaleeddies
4 </dc:subject>
5 <dc:subject>Germany--History--1933-1945</dc:subject>
6 <dc:subject>info:eu-repo/classification/ddc/641</dc:subject>
7 <dc:subject>Anatomy</dc:subject>
```

1.15 Description (MA)

1.15.1 DC Field

dc:description

1.15.2 Usage

Mandatory when applicable

1.15.3 Usage Instruction

This element is used for a textual description of the content. When a resource consists of several separate physical object files, do not use `dc:description` to list the URLs of these files.

1.15.4 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.15.5 Example

```

1 <dc:description>
2   Foreword [by] Hazel Anderson; Introduction; The scientific heresy:
3   transformation of a society; Consciousness as causal reality [etc]
4 </dc:description>
5
6 <dc:description>
7   A number of problems in quantum state and system identification are
8   addressed.
9 </dc:description>

```

1.16 Publisher (MA)

1.16.1 DC Field

`dc:publisher`

1.16.2 Usage

Mandatory when applicable

1.16.3 DCMI Definition

An entity responsible for making the resource available. Examples of a Publisher include a person, an organization, or a service. Typically, the name of a Publisher should be used to indicate the entity.

1.16.4 Usage Instruction

The (commercial or non-commercial) publisher of the resource; not the (sub)institution the author is affiliated with. Publisher is used only in the bibliographic / functional sense, not an organisational one. Use only the full name of the given (commercial) publisher, not the name of an organization or institute that is otherwise [in a broader sense] associated with the creator.

With university publications place the name of the faculty and/or research group or research school after the name of the university. In the case of organizations where there is clearly a hierarchy present, list the parts of the hierarchy from largest to smallest, separated by full stops. If it is not clear whether there is a hierarchy present, or unclear which is the larger or smaller portion of the body, give the name as it appears in the eprint.

The use of publisher names from authority lists constructed according to local or national thesaurus files is optional.

1.16.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Contributor (R)*
- *Creator (M)*

In most cases the publisher and the creator are not the same.

1.16.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.16.7 Example

```
1 <dc:publisher>
2   Loughborough University. Department of Computer Science
3 </dc:publisher>
4 <dc:publisher>John Wiley & Sons, Inc. (US)</dc:publisher>
```

1.17 Contributor (R)

1.17.1 DC Field

dc:contributor

1.17.2 Usage

Recommended

1.17.3 DCMI Definition

An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource. Examples of a Contributor include a person, an organization, or a service. Typically, the name of a Contributor should be used to indicate the entity.

1.17.4 Usage Instruction

Examples of contributors are: a supervisor, editor, technician or data collector.

Personal names should be listed as: see instructions under Creator. A “promotor”, i.e. a professor supervising a student’s work for a doctor’s degree - is considered a contributor of a dissertation in his or her role as promotor/examiner. In less-rich Unqualified DC it is difficult to express all roles in different contexts. In the PhD thesis as a document, the key figures are the author and the supervisor. In the overall PhD process other roles are involved, such as committee members and the Master of Ceremonies, but in Unqualified these roles have to be sacrificed.

In the case of organizations : see instructions under Creator The inclusion of personal and corporate name headings from authority lists constructed according to local or national thesaurus files is optional.

1.17.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Publisher (MA)*
- *Creator (M)*

The DC element `contributor` describes the scientist(s) that has/have made contributions to the given scientific output, not as a primary creator or (commercial) publisher.

1.17.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.17.7 Example

```

1 <dc:contributor>Evans, R. J.</dc:contributor>
2 <dc:contributor>
3   International Human Genome Sequencing Consortium
4 </dc:contributor>

```

1.18 Publication Date (M)

1.18.1 DC Field

`dc:date`

1.18.2 Usage

Mandatory

1.18.3 DCMI Definition

A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource. Typically, Date will be associated with the creation or availability of the resource. Recommended best practice for encoding the date value is defined in a profile of ISO 8601 [W3CDTF] and follows the YYYY-MM-DD format.

1.18.4 Usage Instruction

The date should be formatted according to the W3C encoding rules for dates and times:

Complete date:

YYYY-MM-DD (e.g. 1997-07-16)

where:

- YYYY [four-digit year] is ‘mandatory’
- MM [two-digit month (01=January, etc.)] is ‘optional’
- DD [two-digit day of month (01 through 31)] is ‘optional’

One date field – Date of Publication:

Often repository systems have more than one date fields that serve different purposes. Date of creation, publication, modified, promotion, etc. Unqualified DC is unable to express all these dates, and for the end-user perspective it is confusing to receive more dates from the service provider. The service provider should make a choice what date- field to pick. Preferably in the end-users perspective the most logical and meaningful date will be the date of publication. To reduce the ambiguity of having a number of date fields without qualifiers, we recommend to reduce the number of fields and present the most meaningful date to the service provider. In most cases this is the date of the publication. In other cases this is the date of promotion of a PhD degree.

No date of publication available:

If no date of publication is available, use any other date available. It is better to use one date than no date at all.

Datestamp additions:

Additions like “Zulu time” should NOT be part of the metadata.

Fuzzy dates:

For fuzzy dates use a logical year that most represents that period, e.g. 1650 instead of 17th century.

To express more about that temporal period, one can use the `dc:coverage` field. A temporal period can be expressed in a standard way when precisely defined (see *Coverage (R)*) or when “fuzzy” or uncertain by free text expressions. A service provider is able to sort dates based on date standards like W3CDTF. Since there is no standard for fuzzy dates for terms like “Renaissance” or “17th Century”, they will simply not appear on date-based query results.

1.18.5 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.18.6 Example

```
1 <dc:date>2000-12-25</dc:date>
2 <dc:date>1978-02</dc:date>
3 <dc:date>1650</dc:date>
```

1.19 Publication Type (M)

1.19.1 DC Field

`dc:type`

1.19.2 Usage

Publication type is used for the following purposes:

- **Mandatory (M):** Publication type (controlled): to indicate the type of publication based on the `info:eu-repo-publication-type-terms` vocabulary.
- **Optional (O):** Publication type (free): to indicate the type of publication based on a local repository vocabulary.

1.19.3 DCMI Definition

The type of scientific output the resource is a manifestation of. In the DC element type the kind of dissemination, or the intellectual and/or content type of the resource is described. It is used to explain to the user what kind of resource he is looking at. Is it a book or an article. Was it written for internal or external use, etc.

1.19.4 Usage Instruction

Publication types (controlled):

The first occurrence of the DC Element type is mandatory and should be used for the type indication of the scientific output based on the `info:eu-repo` publication type vocabulary:

- `info:eu-repo/semantics/article`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/bachelorThesis`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/masterThesis`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/doctoralThesis`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/book`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/bookPart`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/review`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/conferenceObject`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/lecture`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/workingPaper`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/preprint`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/report`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/annotation`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/contributionToPeriodical`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/patent`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/other`

Publication types (free text):

The second occurrence of the DC Element type is optional and should be used for the subtype indication of the scientific output.

1.19.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Format (R)*

DC element *type* describes the kind of academic output the resource is a representation of. DC element ‘format’ describes the media type of this resource.

1.19.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.19.7 Example

```
<dc:type>info:eu-repo/semantics/article</dc:type>
```

1.20 Publication Version (R)

1.20.1 DC Field

dc:type

1.20.2 Usage

Recommended: Version (controlled): to indicate the status in the publication process.

1.20.3 DCMI Definition

1.20.4 Usage Instruction

Version (controlled):

be used for the version of the scientific output based on the DRIVER-version `info:eu-repo` version terms. vocabulary. Use exact text as shown in the list below. For more information about the version model see <http://www.lse.ac.uk/library/versions/>.

- `info:eu-repo/semantics/draft`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/submittedVersion`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/acceptedVersion`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/publishedVersion`
- `info:eu-repo/semantics/updatedVersion`

1.20.5 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.20.6 Example

```
<dc:type>info:eu-repo/semantics/publishedVersion</dc:type>
```

1.21 Format (R)

1.21.1 DC Field

dc:format

1.21.2 Usage

Recommended

1.21.3 DCMI Definition

The physical or digital manifestation of the resource. Typically, Format may include the media-type or dimensions of the resource. Format may be used to determine the software, hardware or other equipment needed to display or operate the resource. Examples of dimensions include size and duration. Recommended best practice is to select a value from a controlled vocabulary (for example, the list of Internet Media Types [MIME] defining computer media formats).

1.21.4 Usage Instruction

Based on best practice, the IANA registered list of Internet Media Types (MIME types) is used to select a term from. For the full list see <http://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types>

If one specific resource (an instance of scientific output) has more than one physical formats (e.g. postscript and pdf) stored as different object files, all formats are mentioned in the DC element format, for example:

- `<dc:format>application/pdf</dc:format>`
- `<dc:format>application/postscript</dc:format>`
- `<dc:format>application/vnd.oasis.opendocument.text</dc:format>`

1.21.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Publication Type (M)*
- *Resource Identifier (M)*

DC element `format` describes the media type of this resource. DC element `type` describes the kind of academic output the resource is a representation of. `dc:identifier` is used to represent manifestations of digital resources.

1.21.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.21.7 Example

```

1 <dc:format>video/quicktime</dc:format>
2 <dc:format>application/pdf</dc:format>
3 <dc:format>application/xml</dc:format>
4 <dc:format>application/xhtml+xml</dc:format>
5 <dc:format>application/html</dc:format>
6 <dc:format>application/vnd.oasis.opendocument.text</dc:format>

```

1.22 Resource Identifier (M)

1.22.1 DC Field

`dc:identifier`

1.22.2 Usage

Mandatory

1.22.3 DCMI Definition

An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.

1.22.4 Usage Instruction

Recommended best practice is to identify the resource by means of a string or number conforming to a formal identification system. Example formal identification systems include the Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), the Uniform Resource Locator (URL), the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), and the URN:NBN.

The ideal use of this element is to use a direct link or a link to a jump-off page (persistent URL) from `dc:identifier` in the metadata record to the digital resource or a jump-off page.

Smart practice:

- use stable URL's
- provide every identifier one can find about the publication.
 - (URL,DOI,URN:NBN,ISBN,ISSN,etc.)
- place the “most appropriate” identifier in the form of a URL at the top of the list of Identifiers. In almost all cases this is the one that will be used by a service provider to let an end-user refer to. This can be a link to a jump-off page or a direct link to the file. Also this can be a direct URL, or a redirection URL, like PURL, HANDLE or other international resolution mechanisms.

1.22.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Relation (O)* (Use `dc:relation` to refer from one version of the resource to another.)
- *Source (R)* (Use `dc:source` for bibliographic citation of the originating resource.)

1.22.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.22.7 Example

In this example the identifiers are sorted so that URLs are given first. The first URL will be considered as “most appropriate” and will be used in e.g. OpenAIRE to let an end-user redirect to. In this case the handle redirects to the jump-off page. A jump-off page is a good way to refer to. The end-user has the opportunity to see more information about the object(s) he has found, see the context and enjoy the other services a local repository has to offer:

```

1 <dc:identifier>http://hdl.handle.net/1234/5628 </dc:identifier>
2 <dc:identifier>http://arno.unimaas.nl/show.cgi?fid=5628 </dc:identifier>
3 <dc:identifier>http://n2t.info/urn:nbn:nl:ui:14123456789</dc:identifier>
4 <dc:identifier>urn:nbn:nl:ui:13-123456789</dc:identifier>
5 <dc:identifier>urn:isbn:123456789</dc:identifier>
6 <dc:identifier>info:doi:10-123456789</dc:identifier>

```

1.23 Source (R)

1.23.1 DC Field

dc:source

1.23.2 Usage

Recommended

1.23.3 DCMI Definition

A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.

1.23.4 Usage Instruction

The present resource may be derived from the Source resource in whole or in part. Recommended best practice is to reference the resource by means of a string or number conforming to a formal identification system.

Best practice: Use only when the described resource is the result of digitization of non-digital originals. Otherwise, use Relation. Optionally metadata about the current location and call number of the digitized publication can be added.

Use: Guidelines for Encoding Bibliographic Citation Information in Dublin Core Metadata (<http://dublincore.org/documents/dc-citation-guidelines/>).

1.23.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Relation (O)*
- *Resource Identifier (M)*

1.23.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.23.7 Example

```
1 <dc:source>Ecology Letters (1461023X) vol.4 (2001) </dc:source>  
2 <dc:source>ISSN: 0928-0987</dc:source>
```

1.24 Language (R)

1.24.1 DC Field

dc:language

1.24.2 Usage

Recommended

1.24.3 DCMI Definition

A language of the intellectual content of the resource.

1.24.4 Usage Instruction

A specific resource (an instance of scientific output) is either written in one human language or more. In these cases all used languages are used in the DC element language. If a specific resource (an instance of scientific output) is written in one human language and is translated into other human languages, each translation does have its own record..

Recommended: ISO 639-x, where x can be 1,2 or 3. Best Practice: we use ISO 639-3 and by doing so we follow: <http://www.sil.org/iso639-3/>

If necessary, repeat this element to indicate multiple languages.

If ISO 639-2 and 639-1 are sufficient for the contents of a repository they can be used alternatively. Since there is a unique mapping this can be done during an aggregation process.

1.24.5 Do Not Confuse With

- Country codes (ISO 3166-1)

1.24.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.24.7 Example

```

1 <dc:language>eng</dc:language>
2 <dc:language>deu</dc:language>
3 <dc:language>nld</dc:language>
4 <dc:language>nld/dut</dc:language>
5 <dc:language>dut</dc:language>
6 <dc:language>nl</dc:language>

```

1.25 Relation (O)

1.25.1 DC Field

dc:relation

1.25.2 Usage

Optional

1.25.3 DCMI Definition

The reference to a related resource.

1.25.4 Usage Instruction

For OpenAIRE-specific use, see sections on *Project Identifier (MA)*, *Alternative Identifier (R)*, *Publication Reference (R)*, and *Dataset Reference (R)*.

Recommended best practice is to reference the resource by means of a string or number conforming to a formal identification system. The DC element `relation` can be used to indicate different kinds of relations between several metadata records. If relations between metadata records are made visible by using metadata the following holds for the distinction between versions (author version and publisher version, preprint, postprint, etc.):

- A metadata record is self-contained
- Different manifestations of one and the same resource (an instance of scientific output that can be described with exactly the same bibliographic metadata, except for the DC element `format`) are linked to one single metadata record using `dc:relation`.

Changes in the metadata other than the DC element `format` leads to creating a new metadata record of this new instance of scientific output which meets all requirements formulated in this document and has a value in the DC element `relation`.

1.25.5 Do Not Confuse With

- *Resource Identifier (M)*
- *Source (R)*

1.25.6 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.25.7 Example

Generic use:

```
1 <dc:relation>http://hdl.handle.net/10</dc:relation>
```

The value of `dc:relation` is the identifier of the other document.

Linking two documents:

```
1 <!-- Document A -->
2 <dc:type>info:eu-repo/semantics/submittedVersion</dc:type>
3 <dc:identifier> http://hdl.handle.net/10</dc:identifier>
4 <dc:relation>http://hdl.handle.net/20</dc:relation>
```

```
1 <!-- Document B -->
2 <dc:type>info:eu-repo/semantics/acceptedVersion</dc:type>
3 <dc:identifier> http://hdl.handle.net/20</dc:identifier>
4 <dc:relation>http://hdl.handle.net/10</dc:relation>
```

1.26 Coverage (R)

1.26.1 DC Field

`dc:coverage`

1.26.2 Usage

Recommended

1.26.3 DCMI Definition

The extent or scope of the content of the resource. Coverage will typically include spatial location (a place name or geographic coordinates), temporal period (a period label, date, or date range) or jurisdiction (such as a named administrative entity).

1.26.4 Usage Instruction

Recommended best practice is to select the value from a controlled vocabulary (for example, the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names or TGN) and that, where appropriate, named places or time periods be used in preference to numeric identifiers as, for example, sets of coordinates or date ranges. If necessary, repeat this element to encode multiple locations or periods.

1.26.5 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.26.6 Example

Example Spatial: ISO 3166:

```
1 <dc:coverage>NL</dc:coverage>
```

Example Spatial: BOX:

```
1 <dc:coverage>
2   name=Western Australia; northlimit=-13.5; southlimit=-35.5;
3   westlimit=112.5; eastlimit=129
4 </dc:coverage>
```

Note: The syntax used here is provisional, and is currently under review as part of the DCMI work on recommending coordinated syntax recommendations for HTML, XML, and RDF. These recommendations and minor editorial changes in this document can be expected to take place in the near future. Point <http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-point/>

1.27 Audience (R)

1.27.1 DC Field

dc:audience

1.27.2 Usage

Recommended

1.27.3 DCMI Definition

A class of entity for whom the resource is intended or useful.

1.27.4 Usage Instruction

A class of entity may be determined by the creator or the publisher or by a third party. On the U.S. Department of Education, Metadata Reference site, an example is given of audiences: <http://www.ed.gov/admin/reference/index.jsp> :

- Administrators
- Community Groups
- Counsellors
- Federal Funds Recipients and Applicants
- Librarians
- News Media
- Other
- Parents and Families
- Policymakers

- Researchers
- School Support Staff
- Student Financial Aid Providers
- Students
- Teachers

1.27.5 Since

DRIVER Guidelines v2

1.27.6 Example

```
1 <dc:audience>Researchers</dc:audience>  
2 <dc:audience>Students</dc:audience>
```